

Optimizing Oxidation Resistance of C/C Composites with Multi-Layer SiC/ZrB₂-Based Coatings for High-Temperature Application

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Carbon/Carbon (C/C) composite consists of carbon as a fiber and carbon as a matrix.

Carbon Fiber + Carbon Matrix

Rocket Engine Nozzle^[1]

Thermal Protection System (TPS) of the Space Shuttle^[2]

- ✓ Excellent strength-to-weight ratio
- ✓ Minimal thermal expansion
- ✓ Maintain mechanical strengths at high temperatures
- ✓ Resistant to thermal shock

Hypersonics^[3]

[1] ISRO, Carbon-Carbon Nozzle for Rocket Engines. https://www.isro.gov.in/ISRO_Develops_Lightweight_Carbon_Carbon_Nozzle_for_Rocket_Engines.html

[2] Space Shuttle thermal protection system – Wikipedia

[3] ASME, <https://www.asme.org/topics-resources/content/ceramics-make-hypersonic-flight-possibility>

Carbon/Carbon composite highly susceptible to oxidation above 450 °C.

Uncoated TGA* Test up to 1000 °C in air

*TGA: Thermogravimetric Analysis

[1] Calo, J. M.; Perkins, M. T. *Carbon N. Y.* **1987**, *25*, 395.

SiC and ZrB₂ coatings provide barrier, reactive, and self-healing protection, making them ideal for high-temperature antioxidative applications.

SiC
Good adhesion and similar CTE

ZrB₂
High melting point and self-healing

Material	*CTE (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)	Melting Point (°C)
C	2.50 ^[1]	3550 ^[1]
SiO ₂	0.55-0.75 ^[2]	1710 ^[2]
SiC	4.30 ^[1]	2700 ^[1]
ZrB ₂	5.9 ^[1]	3245 ^[1]
HfB ₂	6.3 ^[1]	3380 ^[1]
HfC	6.8 ^[1]	3890 ^[1]
Al ₂ O ₃	7.92-10.34 ^[2]	2369 ^[2]

*CTE: Coefficient of thermal expansion

[1] Jin, Xiaochao, et al. "Advances in oxidation and ablation resistance of high and ultra-high temperature ceramics modified or coated carbon/carbon composites." *Journal of the European ceramic Society* 38.1 (2018): 1-28.

[2] Nielsen, T. H., and M. H. Leibold. "Thermal expansion in air of ceramic oxides to 2200° C." *Journal of the American Ceramic Society* 46.8 (1963): 381-387.

The multilayer coating strategy demonstrated strong effectiveness.

Pack Cementation (PC)

- ✓ Thermal Stress Management
- ✓ Improved Adhesion and Durability
- ✓ SiC

Chemical Vapor Deposition (CVD)

- ✓ Fills the pores
- ✓ Dense SiC

Slurry Coating (S)

- ✓ Enhanced Oxidation Resistance
- ✓ Self-Healing Capability
- ✓ ZrB₂

Number of Layers ?

Order of Sequence ?

Pack Cementation Provides a Well-Adhered and Uniform SiC Coating with Enhanced Oxidation Resistance

Pack Powders

Ball Mixing

Packed in Crucible

Graphitization Furnace

Ultrasonic Cleaning

Powder Components

PC	5B-PC
55 wt% Si	57 wt% Si
10 wt% C	8 wt% C
5 wt% Al ₂ O ₃	5 wt% Al ₂ O ₃
30 wt% SiC	25 wt% SiC
	5 wt% B

Boron modified PC
(5B-PC)

1900 °C

Dry at 100 °C

The CVD setup using **HMDS*** and H₂ enables controlled SiC deposition on C/C composites, with precise heating steps to ensure uniform coating.

Step	Heating Rate (°C/min)	Final Temp (°C)	Purpose
Initial Heating	20	800	Preheat with H ₂ only
HMDS Ramp	1	950	SiC Deposition

HMDS: nontoxic, liquid SiC precursor

Methyl trichlorosilane (MTS)

Methyldichlorosilane (MDCS)

Slurry enables uniform deposition of a ZrB₂–SiC-based self-healing layer with high-temperature oxidation resistance.

Solution Composition

13 wt% Tetrahydrofuran (THF)
16 wt% SMP-10 (SiC precursor)
71 wt% ZrB₂ (High-Temp Ceramic, HTC)

Magnetic Stirring

Sample Dipping

Heat Treatment

Heat Treatment Program

T ₁ (°C)	T ₂ (°C)	Rate (°C/min)	Dwell (h)
25	100	1	1
100	300	1	1
300	600	1	1
600	1000	2	1

Self healing equation

Uncoated sample

Coated sample

Muffle Furnace oxidation used to find mass loss of coated C/C composites at 1000 °C in **air atmosphere** of different time interval

Sample (15x25x3 mm)

Furnace (1000 °C)

Weight Measurement

Time	Interval
Initially	2 h
12 ⁺ h	12 h

Pack cementation (PC) works best as a base layer, enhances stability of multilayer coating performance

Single layer

Remaining mass after 60-hour oxidation

Distinct ceramic phases formed corresponding to coating technique, converted into protective oxides such as SiO_2 and ZrO_2 upon oxidation

XRD of Single layer

Double layers with slurry (PC+S, 5B-PC+S) exhibit superior oxidation resistance compared to CVD external layer

PC with boron addition shows better performance irrespective of coating sequence

Three layers

Cross-section of oxidized sample 60 h (3 layers)
5B-PC+CVD+S

CVD as the outer layer limits ZrO_2 formation, reducing self-healing ability

XRD after oxidation (3 Layers)

No ZrO_2 peak

Three-Layer coating fails under long term oxidation (1000°C)

Incorporation of CVD as a fourth and outer layer diminishes the protective performance of the coating system

Four layers

After 60 h oxidation

Mass Gain 2%

5B-PC+CVD+S

Three layers

Mass Loss 16%

5B-PC+CVD+S+CVD

Four layers

For 4-layer samples, CVD as 2nd layer or 3rd layer in between two slurry coatings have similar oxidation resistance.

CVD as a sixth and outer layer, is stable if the base layer is boron modified PC.

Five and six layers

Conclusions

Number of layers	Time (hour)
3 (PC/5B-PC+CVD+S)	~100-200
4 (Any combination S/O*)	~ 250
5 (S/O)	~ 400
6 (5B-PC base CVD/O*)	~ 500

S/O* = S as an outer layer

CVD/O* = CVD as an outer layer

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Questions ?

Carbon Fiber + Carbon Matrix

Uncoated C/C composite TGA* test up to 800 °C in air

Number of layers	Time (hour)
3 (PC/5B-PC+CVD+S)	~100-200
4 (Any combination S/O)	~ 250
5 (S/O)	~ 400
6 (5B-PC base CVD/O)	~ 500